

Investigating chlorine consumption through semi-mechanistic modeling and its implications for trihalomethane formation: A comparison of diverse drinking water

Ehsan Ranjbar^{a,b,*} , Dominik Kaczmarek^{a,b}, Hamed Khorasani^c, Aki Sebastian Ruhl^{a,b}

^a Technische Universität Berlin, Faculty III–Process Sciences, Institute of Environmental Technology, Chair of Water Treatment, KF4, Str. des 17. Juni 135, 10623 Berlin, Germany

^b German Environment Agency (UBA), Section II 3.3, Schichauweg 58, 12307 Berlin, Germany

^c California Department of Water Resources, 3310 El Camino Ave, Sacramento, CA 95821, USA

HIGHLIGHTS

- Most tap water samples showed rapid chlorine consumption within 2 h of dosing.
- UV₂₅₄ absorbance showed strong correlation with chlorine consumption.
- Predictive model accurately described chlorine consumption over time.
- Trihalomethane levels varied widely in drinking water samples in Germany.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Tap water
Chlorination
Disinfection byproducts
Natural organic matter
Emerging pollutants

ABSTRACT

In many regions, drinking water disinfection is crucial for the inactivation of microorganisms. However, chemical reactions between chlorine and natural organic matter and inorganic compounds can result in unwanted formation of disinfection by-products (DBPs). 25 non-chlorinated tap water samples from different regions of Germany were chlorinated to evaluate the chlorine consumption and formation of DBPs. Most of the water samples quickly consumed the initially dosed chlorine (NaOCl as 1 mg/L Cl₂), leaving less than 10% residual chlorine after 2 h. A strong correlation between ultra-violet absorption at a wavelength of 254 nm (UV₂₅₄) and chlorine consumption was observed. A mathematical model using this correlation could well predict chlorine consumption over time. The model can be used to design chlorine booster stations in water distribution networks. The formation of trihalomethanes (THM) including trichloromethane (chloroform), tribromomethane (bromoform), bromodichloromethane, and dibromochloromethane was analyzed. The results revealed varying levels of THM. While the highest total THM concentrations reached 93.8 µg/L, the lowest concentration was 10.7 µg/L.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Ehsan.Ranjbar@TU-Berlin.de (E. Ranjbar).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2025.124673>

Received 30 April 2025; Received in revised form 26 June 2025; Accepted 24 September 2025

Available online 24 September 2025

0043-1354/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

The disinfection of drinking water might be an issue of great importance for inactivating microorganisms. Chlorination, ultra-violet (UV) irradiation, and ozonation are common methods for disinfecting drinking water in municipal treatment plants. However, for disinfecting water in distribution systems, chlorination remains the only practical option for ensuring safe delivery to consumers. Chlorine-based disinfectants offer several benefits, including high effectiveness against various pathogens, residual activity in the distribution network, low cost, and ease of use (Gilca et al., 2020; Köhler et al., 2018; Ku et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Parveen et al., 2022; Rand et al., 2008).

Natural organic matter (NOM) significantly consumes chlorine, and the chlorine demand is reported to strongly relate to the concentration of NOM (Ramírez Zamora et al., 2004; Shurvell et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2012). Consequently, chlorine consumption varies greatly among different water matrices. It is important to adjust the chlorine doses accordingly and to potentially position chlorine booster stations in water distribution networks to maintain an adequate chlorine residual, thereby preventing microbial re-growth (Seth et al., 2019).

Climate change is causing a progressive increase in temperatures and more frequent floods, which lead to higher NOM levels and subsequently increased chlorine demands and faster chlorine consumptions in water matrices (Lipczynska-Kochany, 2018; Shakhawat et al., 2024). Previous researches also reported a significant rise in NOM concentrations over the past decades in surface waters (Evans et al., 2005; Skjelkvåle et al., 2005). High NOM concentrations combined with increasing temperatures might increase microbial regrowth and compromising microbial stability in water distribution networks (Valdivia-García et al., 2019). Under these circumstances, chlorination might become an inevitable choice.

Besides the advantages of chlorination, there are some disadvantages. The main drawback is the formation of disinfection by-products

(DBPs), which result from reactions of chlorine with NOM and inorganic constituents (Bond et al., 2012; Gang et al., 2003; Shah et al., 2024). The World Health Organization (WHO) has classified DBPs as “harmful to human health,” and most of them are reported to be carcinogenic, particularly affecting organs such as the breast, brain, liver, kidneys, thyroid, lungs and bladder (Costet et al., 2011; Dad et al., 2018; Gilca et al., 2020; Hebert et al., 2010). Additionally, some DBPs have been linked to birth defects (Quintiliani et al., 2018; Wright et al., 2017).

To date, over 700 DBPs have been identified in tap water (Zhang et al., 2023). Some prominent DBPs, such as trihalomethanes (THM), haloacetic acids (HAAs), bromate and chlorate are regulated in many countries. However, most DBPs remain unregulated. The European Union has regulated THM including trichloromethane (chloroform), tribromomethane (bromoform), bromodichloromethane, and dibromochloromethane, as well as HAAs including monochloro-, dichloro-, and trichloro-acetic acid, and mono- and dibromo-acetic acid, along with chlorite and bromate (Directive (EU) 2020/2184, 2020).

Lee et al. (2013) studied the levels of THM and HAAs in tap water from six water treatment facilities in Seoul, Korea, and found that the most commonly detected DBPs were dichloroacetic acid, bromodichloromethane, trichloroacetic acid, and chloroform. The total THM concentration varied up to 49.5 µg/L (Lee et al., 2013).

Climate change is expected to significantly impact DBP formation; a previous study showed that a 1.8 °C rise in temperature could lead to a 39% increase in THM levels by 2050, under a mid-range scenario (Valdivia-García et al., 2019). Another study also reported a strong correlation between rising temperatures and increased THM formation in drinking water systems (Valdivia-García et al., 2016).

While some waterworks and distribution systems in Germany apply chlorine-based disinfection, chlorine is not applied in Berlin and many other regions. Given the influence of climate change, chlorination might become essential in the future to ensure the delivery of safe drinking water. Transitioning from non-chlorinated to chlorinated systems requires a thorough evaluation of chlorine demand and formation of DBPs.

NOM compositions depend on watersheds, physico-chemical properties of aquifers, storm water events, and (hydro)geological properties (Li et al., 2020; Siddique et al., 2023; Zeeshan et al., 2025). In this regard, different source waters require different chlorine doses.

To our knowledge, no screening has been conducted on a significant number of currently non-chlorinated water samples for chlorine

Fig. 1. Locations of drinking water sampling sites across Germany.

Table 1
Water quality variables of tap water samples.

Sample	DOC (mg/L)	UVA ₂₅₄ (1/cm)	Bromide (mg/L)
Berlin 1	4.4	0.107	0.098
Berlin 2	3.7	0.098	0.105
Berlin 3	4.1	0.098	0.132
Berlin 4	3.8	0.102	0.077
Bielefeld	1.7	0.053	0.036
Braunschweig	1.9	0.057	0.026
Dresden	2.9	0.048	0.021
Essen	2.1	0.036	0.067
Frankfurt	1.1	0.065	0.051
Greifswald	3.1	0.090	0.078
Hannover 1	3.9	0.096	0.085
Hannover 2	4.4	0.110	0.077
Halle	5.1	0.052	0.018
Herford	0.6	0.051	0.059
Ingolstadt	2.7	0.023	0.018
Köln	0.5	0.051	0.063
Ludwigshafen	1.9	0.080	0.092
Lüder	3.1	0.066	0.046
Mildstedt	2.8	0.033	0.119
Magdeburg	3.9	0.100	0.078
Münster	1.6	0.062	0.057
Rostock	5.7	0.111	0.093
Schwerin	3.7	0.077	0.060
Stuttgart	1.1	0.033	0.005
Zingst	5.2	0.105	0.071

Fig. 2. Correlations between initial DOC concentrations and residual chlorine after contact times of 2 to 120 min.

consumption and THM formation. Additionally, no predictive model for chlorine consumption based on easily analyzed bulk parameters is currently available. The present study aimed to quantify the bulk parameters including dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and ultra-violet absorbance at 254 nm (UVA_{254}), along with chlorine consumption and their potential relationships in a comprehensive set of 25 drinking water samples. Specifically, the objectives were 1) to investigate the relationships between bulk parameters and chlorine consumption, 2) to derive a mathematical model to predict chlorine consumption, 3) to apply the model to all water samples, 4) to analyze the formation of THM in drinking water samples and 5) to explore correlations between bulk parameters and THM formation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Water samples

25 samples were collected from households in different non-chlorinated water distribution systems across Germany (Fig. 1) in winter (December and January) as described by Ingold et al. (2023). Water quality parameters relevant for chlorine consumption and formation of DBPs, including DOC, UVA_{254} and bromide concentrations, are provided in Table 1. More details on more water constituents are

provided by Zeeshan et al. (2025).

2.2. Chlorination experiments

Defined volumes of a sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) stock solution were added to 10 mL amber glass bottles containing drinking water samples. The bottles were shaken at room temperature on a horizontal shaker. For each experiment, 1 mg/L Cl_2 were dosed into several 10 mL drinking water samples that were tightly sealed subsequently. 1 mg/L Cl_2 was chosen to comply with the German drinking water regulation, as the maximum allowable chlorine dose is 1.2 mg/L Cl_2 (UBA, 2023). After a predefined contact time, the respective sample was opened, and a powdered mixture of diethyl-p-phenylene diamine (DPD), EDTA, Na_2HPO_4 , and KH_2PO_4 was added. The samples were analyzed by a calibrated photometer (Lambda 2, Perkin-Elmer, USA) to determine residual free chlorine in the samples.

For THM formation, 1 mg/L Cl_2 was dosed into 10 mL drinking water samples in 20 mL amber vials, capped, and stored at room temperature for gas chromatography (GC) analysis. All samples were prepared in triplicate to check the consistency of the results.

Fig. 3. Correlations between initial UV₂₅₄ and residual chlorine after contact times of 2 to 120 min.

Fig. 4. (a) Variation of α coefficient over time and (b) comparison of observed and predicted residual chlorine concentrations in drinking water samples.

2.3. THM analyses

The concentrations of THM were measured using a headspace gas chromatograph coupled to a mass spectrometer (HS-GC-MS, Agilent,

Santa Clara, USA). The GC (Agilent 7890A) was equipped with a HP-5ms Ultra Inert (19091S-436UI) column with a length of 60 m, an inner diameter of 0.25 mm and 0.25 μ m film thickness. The MS (Agilent 5975C) used an electron beam for ionization while filtering the ions with

Fig. 5. Measured and modelled relative residual chlorine concentrations (1 mg/L Cl_2 dosage) in different non-chlorinated tap water samples over time.

a quadrupole. The headspace sampling [Gerstel MPS system] was performed using 20 mL amber glass bottles. The samples were shaken using an agitator for 40 min at 60 °C. 1 mL of gas sample was injected with a split 1:10 at 210 °C.

The GC was operated with a flow of 0.6 mL/min of helium. The temperature program started at 40 °C, then increased to 60 °C at a rate of 4 °C/min, followed by a rise to 190 °C at 10 °C/min. The final temperature was held for additional 5 min, with a total run time of 28 min.

2.4. Modelling of chlorine consumption

The chlorine consumption was modeled as a first-order reaction as follows:

$$C(t) = C_0 \exp(-kt) \quad (1)$$

$C(t)$ is the chlorine concentrations (mg/L) at time t (min), C_0 is the initial concentration of chlorine, and k is the reaction rate coefficient (1/min).

To estimate the reaction rate coefficient of a mechanistic model, Eq. 1 can be rearranged to Eq. 2 for calculation of k at each time step for each sample:

$$k = -\frac{1}{t} \ln \left(\frac{C(t)}{C_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

To develop a semi-mechanistic model for chlorine consumption, the reaction rate coefficient was estimated as a function of relevant water quality parameters. In the present study, k is simulated as a function of other water quality parameters to derive a dependent constant rate. A relationship between the reaction rate coefficient (k) and a water quality parameter (C^*) was hypothesized, expressed as $k = \alpha C^*$, where α is a proportionality constant. Given that C^* is a known parameter, substituting this relationship into Eq. 2 shifts the unknown parameter from k to α , resulting in Eq. 3:

$$\alpha = -\frac{1}{t.C^*} \ln \left(\frac{C(t)}{C_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

The physical interpretability of the coefficient (α) depends on the units of the water quality parameter (C^*), and it may or may not align with known chemical and physical relationships.

Fig. 6. Residual chlorine (1 mg/L Cl_2 dosage) after 24 h contact time in tap water samples.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Impacts of DOC and UV_{254} on chlorine consumption

The considered samples cover a substantial range of DOC concentrations and UV_{254} as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Residual chlorine concentrations in the samples after different contact times correlate reasonably well with the DOC and UV_{254} . The initial UV_{254} and the chlorine consumption correlate more strongly than DOC and chlorine consumption.

UVA_{254} , which reflects the presence of bulk organic matter and the UV absorbance of mainly aromatic and unsaturated compounds (Weishaar et al., 2003), may correlate more strongly than DOC due to its better indication of chlorine-consuming substances. Molecules with aromatic structures consume most of the chlorine during the chlorination (Al-Omari et al., 2014). Therefore, UV-absorbing compounds appear to react with chlorine more selectively than other fractions of the DOC, resulting in a stronger relationship.

3.2. Prediction of chlorine consumption

Given the strong relation between chlorine consumption and UV_{254} (Fig. 3), reaction rate coefficient was hypothesized that can be simulated as a function of UV_{254} , i.e., $k = \alpha UV_{254}$. By substituting this assumption in Eq. 1, the equation becomes as follows (Eq. 4):

$$C(t) = C_0 \exp(-\alpha UV_{254} t) \quad (4)$$

Calculation of α is similar to that of k as explained before, the Eq. 2 would be re-written as follows (Eq. 5):

Fig. 7. THM formation after dosing 1 mg/L Cl_2 to non-chlorinated tap water samples (error bars represent standard deviations of triplicates).

$$\alpha = -\frac{1}{t \times UV_{254}} \ln\left(\frac{C(t)}{C_0}\right) \quad (5)$$

As shown in Fig. 4a, α is a time dependent constant with an estimated power function as follows:

$$\alpha = 3.5871 t^{-0.558} \quad (6)$$

Substituting Eq. 6 into Eq. 5 results in Eq. 7, which represents the proposed model for predicting residual chlorine in drinking water samples using UV_{254} (1/cm) as a quick estimator:

$$C_t = C_0 e^{-3.587 \times UV_{254} \times t^{0.442}} \quad (7)$$

The predicted residual chlorine is presented and compared with the observed values in Fig. 4b, showing a strong correlation and demonstrating the applicability of the proposed model for predicting residual chlorine in drinking water samples.

3.3. Chlorine consumption

Tap waters from Berlin, Frankfurt, Greifswald, Hannover, Ludwigshafen, Magdeburg, Rostock, Schwerin, and Zingst exhibited rapid chlorine consumptions, depleting most of the initially dosed chlorine and leaving less than 10% residual chlorine after 120 min (Fig. 5). Tap waters from Essen, Ingolstadt, Köln, Mildstedt, and Stuttgart showed

lower chlorine consumption, with approximately 40% or more residual chlorine. These samples also had relatively higher UV_{254} values compared to the others.

In most cases, the predicted curves closely follow the observed chlorine concentrations, indicating that the model based on UVA_{254} successfully captures the chlorine decay in the samples. Overall, the results demonstrate a strong agreement between the predicted residual chlorine using UV_{254} values and the observed data across most samples.

To validate the proposed model, one chlorination experiment was conducted using a new tap water sample from Berlin to verify the applicability of the model to samples outside the current dataset. The results show good agreement between the modelled and observed data and demonstrate that the proposed model predicts the measured data well (Fig. S1). It is worth noting that the proposed model was developed using non-chlorinated samples and has not been validated for chlorinated samples.

3.4. Residual chlorine after one day

The residual chlorine concentrations after 24 h revealed that in most of the water samples (14 out of 25), the dosed chlorine was fully consumed (Fig. 6). Stuttgart showed the highest residual chlorine levels (around 40%), while Ingolstadt, Halle, Herford, Köln, and Mildstedt retained 10 to 30% residual chlorine. The remaining samples contained less than 10% residual chlorine after 24 h.

3.5. Formation of THM

Triplicate chlorination experiments demonstrated reproducible formation of THM, including trichloromethane, tribromomethane, bromodichloromethane, and dibromochloromethane, with varying levels observed across different water samples (Fig. 7). When considering THM in samples individually, trichloromethane was the dominant THM in all samples except for Mildstedt. The elevated bromide concentration in Mildstedt (0.119 mg/L), the highest among all the samples, might have led to the increased formation of brominated THM. Determining proportion of brominated THM shows that bromodichloromethane is the dominant brominated THM in most of the samples (Fig. S2).

Stuttgart had the highest trichloromethane level among the samples, which may be attributed to its highest residual chlorine concentration after 24 h of contact time, allowing more interaction between chlorine and THM precursors. In some samples, such as those from Berlin, rapid chlorine consumption may reduce THM formation, possibly due to the reduced contact time between chlorine and THM precursors. Bromodichloromethane was the dominant brominated THM in most samples, while tribromomethane was not detected in most samples.

No strong individual correlation was observed between THM and DOC or UV_{254} (Fig. S3a and b), which may be attributed to varying levels of bromide and other THM precursors across different water matrices, affecting the strength of correlation with each parameter. Similarly, the correlation between brominated THM and bromide concentrations was weak, with an R^2 value of 0.17 (Fig. S3c), probably due to different DOC concentrations, NOM composition and respective consumptions in the tap water samples.

4. Conclusions

The results indicate that 1 mg/L chlorine is consumed within 24 h in most of the tap water samples that have not been chlorinated before. A mathematical model was derived to estimate chlorine consumption over time based on UVA_{254} . The model predicts chlorine consumptions reasonably well for drinking waters that have not been chlorinated. The formation of THM was found to be significant in many samples. Trichloromethane was confirmed as the dominant THM and brominated THM were also detected in all samples. Although a strong correlation was observed between bulk parameters, particularly UV_{254} , and chlorine

consumption, no strong correlation was found between THM formation and these parameters, which may be attributed to varying levels of bromide and other THM precursors across different water matrices. However, further investigations are needed to include other DBPs, such as HAAs, which may be more closely associated with DOC or UV absorbing precursors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ehsan Ranjbar: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dominik Kaczmarek:** Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Hamed Khorasani:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Aki Sebastian Ruhl:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the European Union under grant agreement No 101081980. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.watres.2025.124673](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2025.124673).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Al-Omari, A., Muhammetoglu, A., Karadirek, E., Jiries, A., Batarseh, M., Topkaya, B., Soyupak, S., 2014. A review on formation and decay kinetics of trihalomethanes in water of different qualities. *CLEAN – Soil Air Water* 42, 1687–1700. <https://doi.org/10.1002/clean.201300347>.
- Bond, T., Goslan, Emma H., Parsons, Simon A., Jefferson, B., 2012. A critical review of trihalomethane and haloacetic acid formation from natural organic matter surrogates. *Environ. Technol. Rev.* 1, 93–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2012.705895>.
- Costet, N., Villanueva, C.M., Jaakkola, J.J.K., Kogevinas, M., Cantor, K.P., King, W.D., Lynch, C.F., Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., Cordier, S., 2011. Water disinfection by-products and bladder cancer: is there a European specificity? A pooled and meta-analysis of European case-control studies. *Occup. Environ. Med.* 68, 379–385. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2010.062703>.
- Dad, A., Jeong, C.H., Wagner, E.D., Plewa, M.J., 2018. Haloacetic acid water disinfection byproducts affect pyruvate dehydrogenase activity and disrupt cellular metabolism. *Env. Sci. Technol.* 52, 1525–1532. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b04290>.
- Directive (EU) 2020/2184, 2020. DIRECTIVE (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament And of the COUNCIL of 16 December 2020 On the Quality of Water Intended For Human Consumption.
- Evans, C.D., Monteith, D.T., Cooper, D.M., 2005. Long-term increases in surface water dissolved organic carbon: observations, possible causes and environmental impacts. *environmental pollution, recovery from acidification in the UK: evidence from 15 years of acid waters monitoring* 137, 55–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2004.12.031>.
- Gang, D., Clevenger, T.E., Banerji, S.K., 2003. Relationship of chlorine decay and THMs formation to NOM size. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 96, 1–12. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3894\(02\)00164-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3894(02)00164-4).
- Gilca, A.F., Teodosiu, C., Fiore, S., Musteret, C.P., 2020. Emerging disinfection byproducts: a review on their occurrence and control in drinking water treatment processes. *Chemosphere* 259, 127476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.127476>.

- Hebert, A., Forestier, D., Lenes, D., Benanou, D., Jacob, S., Arfi, C., Lambomez, L., Levi, Y., 2010. Innovative method for prioritizing emerging disinfection by-products (DBPs) in drinking water on the basis of their potential impact on public health. *Water Res* 44, 3147–3165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2010.02.004>.
- Ingold, V., Kämpfe, A., Ruhl, A.S., 2023. Screening for 26 per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in German drinking waters with support of residents. *Eco-Environ. Health* 2, 235–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eehl.2023.08.004>.
- Köhler, A.T., Rodloff, A.C., Labahn, M., Reinhardt, M., Truyen, U., Speck, S., 2018. Efficacy of sodium hypochlorite against multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacteria. *J. Hosp. Infect.* 100, e40–e46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhin.2018.07.017>.
- Ku, T.S., Walraven, C.J., Lee, S.A., 2018. *Candida auris*: disinfectants and implications for infection control. *Front Microbiol* 9, 726.
- Lee, J., Kim, E.S., Roh, B.S., Eom, S.W., Zoh, K.D., 2013. Occurrence of disinfection by-products in tap water distribution systems and their associated health risk. *Env. Monit Assess* 185, 7675–7691. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-013-3127-1>.
- Li, L.P., Huang, W.L., Yang, M.T., Liu, Y., Bowden, R.D., Simpson, M.J., Lajtha, K., Tian, L.Q., Wang, J.J., 2020. Chlorination of soil-derived dissolved organic matter: long term nitrogen deposition does not increase terrestrial precursors of toxic disinfection byproducts. *Water Res* 185, 116271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116271>.
- Li, T., Wang, Z., Wang, C., Huang, J., Zhou, M., 2022. Chlorination in the pandemic times: the current state of the art for monitoring chlorine residual in water and chlorine exposure in air. *Sci. Total Environ.* 838, 156193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156193>.
- Lipczynska-Kochany, E., 2018. Effect of climate change on humic substances and associated impacts on the quality of surface water and groundwater: a review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 640–641, 1548–1565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.05.376>.
- Parveen, N., Chowdhury, S., Goel, S., 2022. Environmental impacts of the widespread use of chlorine-based disinfectants during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Env. Sci Pollut Res* 29, 85742–85760. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-18316-2>.
- Quintiliani, C., Di Cristo, C., Leopardi, A., 2018. Vulnerability assessment to trihalomethane exposure in water distribution systems. *Water (Basel)* 10, 912. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10070912>.
- Ramírez Zamora, R.M., Seux, R., Durán Moreno, A., 2004. Influence of ozonation and adsorption processes onto the chlorine demand of surface natural water. *Water Supply* 4, 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2004.0105>.
- Rand, J.L., Shupe, G., Gagnon, G.A., 2008. Synergistic benefits between ultraviolet light and chlorine-based disinfectants for the inactivation of *Escherichia coli*. *Water Qual. Res. J.* 43, 63–68. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wqrj.2008.008>.
- Seth, A., Hackebeil, G.A., Haxton, T., Murray, R., Laird, C.D., Klise, K.A., 2019. Evaluation of chlorine booster station placement for water security. In: Muñoz, S.G., Laird, C.D., Realf, M.J. (Eds.), *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering, Proceedings of the 9 International Conference on Foundations of Computer-Aided Process Design*. Elsevier, pp. 463–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818597-1.50074-6>.
- Shah, M., Mazhar, Mohd.A., Ahmed, S., Lew, B., Khalil, N., 2024. Recent trends in controlling the disinfection by-products before their formation in drinking water: a review. In: Madhav, S., Mazhar, M.A., Ahmed, S., Kumar, P., Mishra, P.K. (Eds.), *Drinking Water Disinfection By-Products: Sources, Fate and Remediation*. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, pp. 177–192. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-49047-7_9.
- Shakhawat (Kiron), M., Gelda, R.K., Moore, K.E., Mukundan, R., Lanzarini-Lopes, M., McBeath, S.T., Guzman, C.D., Reckhow, D., 2024. Impact of storm events on disinfection byproduct precursors in a drinking water source in the Northeastern United States. *Water Res* 255, 121445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2024.121445>.
- Shurvell, T., Farago, L., Jegatheesan, V., Shu, L., 2015. Removal of natural organic matter through membrane filtration and subsequent effect on disinfectant decay. *Desalin. Water Treat* 54, 881–889. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2014.893210>.
- Siddique, M.S., Lu, H., Xiong, X., Fareed, H., Graham, N., Yu, W., 2023. Exploring impacts of water-extractable organic matter on pre-ozonation followed by nanofiltration process: insights from pH variations on DBPs formation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 876, 162695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162695>.
- Skjelkvåle, B.L., Stoddard, J.L., Jeffries, D.S., Tørseth, K., Høgåsen, T., Bowman, J., Mannio, J., Monteith, D.T., Mosello, R., Rogora, M., Rzychon, D., Vesely, J., Wieting, J., Wilander, A., Worsztynowicz, A., 2005. Regional scale evidence for improvements in surface water chemistry 1990–2001. *Environmental Pollution, Recovery from acidification in the UK: evidence from 15 years of acid waters monitoring* 137, 165–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2004.12.023>.
- UBA, 2023. Bekanntmachung der liste zulässiger aufbereitungsstoffe und desinfektionsverfahren gemäß § 20 der trinkwasserordnung.
- Valdivia-Garcia, M., Weir, P., Frogbrook, Z., Graham, D.W., Werner, D., 2016. Climatic, geographic and operational determinants of trihalomethanes (THMs) in drinking water systems. *Sci. Rep* 6, 35027. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep35027>.
- Valdivia-Garcia, M., Weir, P., Graham, D.W., Werner, D., 2019. Predicted impact of climate change on trihalomethanes formation in drinking water treatment. *Sci. Rep* 9, 9967. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-46238-0>.
- Weishaar, J.L., Aiken, G.R., Bergamaschi, B.A., Fram, M.S., Fujii, R., Mopper, K., 2003. Evaluation of specific ultraviolet absorbance as an indicator of the chemical composition and reactivity of dissolved organic carbon. *Env. Sci. Technol* 37, 4702–4708. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es030360x>.
- Wright, J.M., Evans, A., Kaufman, J.A., Rivera-Núñez, Z., Narotsky, M.G., 2017. Disinfection by-product exposures and the risk of specific cardiac birth defects. *Env. Health Perspect* 125, 269–277. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP103>.
- Zeeshan, M., Ingold, V., Saal, L., Höra, C., Kämpfe, A., Ruhl, A.S., 2025. Compositions and concentrations of dissolved organic matter, selected elements and anions in German drinking waters. *J. Env. Manage* 376, 124459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.124459>.
- Zhang, H., Zhang, Y., Shi, Q., Hu, J., Chu, M., Yu, J., Yang, M., 2012. Study on transformation of natural organic matter in source water during chlorination and its chlorinated products using ultrahigh resolution mass spectrometry. *Env. Sci. Technol* 46, 4396–4402. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es203587q>.
- Zhang, J., Ye, D., Fu, Q., Chen, M., Lin, H., Zhou, X., Deng, W., Xu, Z., Sun, H., Hong, H., 2023. The combination of multiple linear regression and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system can accurately predict trihalomethane levels in tap water with fewer water quality parameters. *Sci. Total Environ.* 896, 165269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165269>.